

Nina: the professor, the mentor, the manager

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Abstract: This short paper is a reflection on who Professor Nina F. Thornhill is and what having her by my side during my PhD at Imperial College London and ever since taught me about academia and about life

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1. INTRODUCTION

Professor Nina F. Thornhill (from this point onwards: Nina) was my supervisor during my PhD at the Department of Chemical Engineering, Imperial College London, between September 2011 and May 2015.

I spent 3.5 years working with Nina, travelling with her to conferences and business meetings, hosting visitors at Imperial College London, organising training courses and outreaching activities.

This short papers aims to give the reader, who may not be as familiar with her as I am, some perspectives on who Nina is, as a professor, mentor, and manager.

Fig. 1. Dr Sara Budinis (left) and Professor Nina F. Thornhill (right) at Dr Budinis' graduation ceremony, 4th May 2016, Imperial College London

2. NINA, THE PROFESSOR

Nina is first and foremost a professor. This is not a factual statement due to her position within academia, it is rather an appreciation of how her seniority has placed her at the right distance from her students, not too far, not too close.

I cannot forget the (numerous) times when I met her hoping to get answers, and instead left with questions. It was painful, but necessary, and made me grow from a needy student to an independent researcher, and especially thinker.

If today I am extremely proud of my PhD title, it is because it reminds me, every time I use it, of who I became, and this is thanks to Nina.

3. NINA, THE MENTOR

Nina is not only a professor. She is also a teacher, and a mentor. She spends time (or I would rather say *invest*) teaching her students, undergraduates but especially postgraduates, about process control, English, and life. The former two are intentional, the latter just happens while you work with her.

The three main lessons I learnt from her are the following ones:

- Thank, always, everyone, even for just doing their job
- Apologise, even when you are not “wrong” – there is always room for improvement
- Answer any question without judging it.

4. NINA, THE MANAGER

Nina is an excellent manager, and has the (rare) ability of avoiding any drama within her team. This is because of the following reasons:

- She says everything that needs to be said, and nothing more than that
- She is extremely fair with her students and post-docs
- She is also extremely clear (once you master the fine art of distinguishing the difference between what an English person says, and means).

Therefore, the working environment in her lab is extremely pleasant, and I am sure whoever had the pleasure to pass through it (students, researchers, visitors) can confirm it.

Nina asks her staff to be the best version of themselves, not to be better than anyone else. This promotes excellence while reducing competitions and frictions within the team.

5. CONCLUSIONS

With this short paper, I would like to thank Nina for having been my supervisor and manager during my PhD, and a mentor ever since. She saw potential and enthusiasm, and made me the person I am today. I am extremely grateful for that, and I am also proud of being part of her academic family tree.